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**The role and importance of the anti-corruption compliance control system
in strengthening anti-corruption measures in state organizations is the key to
transparency**

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Annotation. The role and importance of the compliance control system in the field of battling corruption in state organizations and the rules governing the relations that make up its activities, the law and other regulatory acts aimed at organizational and legal regulation of the compliance control system, as well as the impact of corruption on state governing bodies and the effect of introducing a compliance control system

Key words. Corruption, compliance control, compliance control system, accountability, transparency.

We know that corruption has been a negative evil in all times and places and has held society back, and for this reason, it has always been criticized. This situation continues in our society today. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Combating Corruption" was adopted in our country based on the recognition of the existence of corruption and the need to fight against it. In it, several concepts, the main principles of fighting against corruption, the main directions of the state policy in the field of fighting against corruption, the state bodies that directly implement the activities to fight against corruption and their powers in this direction, measures to prevent corruption are shown.

The term corruption is derived from the Latin word "corruptum", which means buying by bribery, selling for bribery, moral violation. It usually means that an official uses the official powers and rights given to him, as well as the related official authority, opportunities and connections for his own personal interests, contrary to the laws and ethics. Corruption has a negative impact on the economy, the current policy of the state within the state and in the international arena. In particular, it will have a negative impact on his image in the international community. The state and society are eroding the foundations of construction. For this reason, it is natural that the need to fight against this disease is increasing. Along with the negative attitude towards the public service and its employees, it leads to a decrease in the quality indicators of personnel.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 29, 2020 "On additional measures to improve the anti-corruption system in the Republic of

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Uzbekistan" No. PF-6013 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 27, 2019 "On measures to further improve the anti-corruption system in the Republic of Uzbekistan" In 2020-2021, one of the main tasks of the newly established anti-corruption agency is to implement an anti-corruption internal control system ("compliance-control") in all state and economic management bodies, state-owned enterprises and enterprises with a state share in the charter capital, including banks. Phased implementation is set.

Anti-corruption compliance control - organizing the activities of state bodies and business entities, banks in accordance with international anti-corruption standards, laws and other regulatory legal documents, timely identification and termination of corruption risks, conflicts of interest, violations of the law and corruption is a preventive system that includes whistleblowing. Based on the tariffs mentioned above, it can be understood that the purpose of implementing compliance control is to prevent corruption risks in the public and private sector and to systematically identify areas where such risks exist, to monitor the factors that cause conflicts of interest on legal and financial grounds, to monitor the activities of various financial, is to create a complex mechanism of systematic protection against economic sanctions and other influences and to maintain a positive image of activity.

From the above, it can be concluded that the compliance control system to fight against corruption was originally created in the USA and is a set of effective mechanisms that serve to identify corruption risks in time, put an end to them, and minimize the risk of corruption.

Also, starting from this year, these experiments were carried out by the Ministry of Construction of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education, the Ministry of Health, as well as the Tashkent city administration, Tashkent regional administration, Mirzo Ulugbek district and Boka district administrations with the support of the United Nations Development Program at the initiative of the Prosecutor General's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan⁵² a compliance control system is being established in state organizations such as Implementation of the compliance service in the above-mentioned companies and organizations is carried out in 4 stages: 1st stage: analysis of the current state of the anti-corruption compliance control service; Stage 2: development or improvement of anti-corruption measures and control mechanisms; Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 17, 2020 No. 72-F. 52 Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 17, 2020 No. 72-F.

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30 Stage 3: introduction of "compliance control" service to combat corruption; Stage 4: work is being carried out in processes such as evaluating the effectiveness of the introduced anti-corruption "compliance control" procedures. Also, on February 17, 2020, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted Order No. 72-F, which indicated that when implementing a compliance control system in state organizations, special attention should be paid to the following: timely identification of corruption risks, putting an end to them, their consequences, eliminate the causes and conditions that enable them and reduce them to a minimum level; increase the accountability and transparency of the activities of state bodies and organizations; regulation of issues of strict compliance by employees with the rules of professional ethics and reporting of conflicts of interest in the performance of official duties and their resolution; strengthening internal control mechanisms over the implementation of departmental measures to combat corruption; introduction of generally recognized international standards and positive foreign experiences in the field of combating corruption¹. Also, in March-April 2020, at the initiative of the General Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in cooperation with 9 state agencies such as the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Transport, the Ministry of Preschool Education, the Ministry of Energy, the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations, the Ministry of Agriculture, the State Customs Committee In order to further improve anti-corruption efficiency in the sectors, the procedure for introducing the compliance control system in stages was agreed and the "Roadmap for further improvement of the fight against corruption for 2020" was approved.².

Also, based on the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 29.06.2020 "On additional measures to improve the system of fighting corruption in the Republic of Uzbekistan" No. PF-6013, the Anti-Corruption Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established. In 2020-2021, one of the main tasks of this office is to gradually introduce an anti-corruption internal control system ("compliance-control") in all state and economic management bodies, state-owned enterprises and enterprises with a state share in the charter capital, including banks.³.

¹Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 17, 2020 No. 72-F

²On March 15, 2020, on the initiative of the General Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the "Roadmap for 2020 on further improvement of the fight against corruption" was adopted.

³Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 29, 2019 No. PF-6013 "On additional measures to improve the system of combating corruption in the Republic of Uzbekistan"

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To conclude, the reforms implemented in the fight against corruption in the activities of the state and private sector are not only the improvement of national legislation based on foreign experiences, but also the implementation of certain international standards, which are used as an effective system in this field, into national legislation. One of them is the compliance control system, which is a set of efficient and effective tools that are widely used in this field.

Through this system, transparency in state organizations will emerge and become a solid legal basis for the fight against evil.

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